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Research Article

From Nature to Nourishment: Evaluating the Efficacy of Herbal Lip Balm Formulations

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ABSTRACT

The lip-care products for everyday basis contains harmful heavy metals and preservatives Other than leaching through the pores on your lips, these heavy metals and other chemicals can also be accidentally ingested. Lip balm formulations are most widely used to enhance the beauty of lips and add glamour touch to the make-up. Lip balms offer a natural way to maintain and promote healthy lips. Current cosmetic lip products are based on use of enormous chemical ingredients which has a various side Effects. Hence, an attempt has made to study the natural ingredients which is used to formulate the natural lip balm. The natural Lip balm can have made using naturally occurring base, oils, colour, flavouring agent etc. Organic lip balm nourishes the lips and help to Get hydrated and protect lips which was affected by the dryness. Organic lip balm can be better option for treatment of various Lip issues. Beetroot lip balm was found to possess the antioxidant activity. The present study was aimed to formulate and evaluate Herbal Lipstick using beet root. The almond oil, bees wax, beet root juice was selected for formulation and evaluation of Herbal Lip balm. The herbal lip balm was formulated as per general method of lip balm formulation. Three formulations (F1, F2, F3) of Herbal Lip balm were prepared and lip balm were evaluated for appearance, melting Point and pH studies gave satisfactory result. F3 was found to be the best and Acceptable formulation among all three formulations whose pH balance 6.5, smoothly texture with no defect as compared to other formulation.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics play an important role in today's lifestyle. Furthermore, the current trend is to go green in most industries, including cosmetics,

towards a more natural lifestyle. Better options are natural foods, herbal medicines and natural cures for healthy living. There is also strong demand for organic plant products. The use of herbal cosmetics has been increased many times in the

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personal care system. Natural products have been used for traditional medicinal purposes around the world for thousands of years. Many of them have pharmacological properties such as antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and cytostatic effects. They have been recognized as useful for human medicine. Cosmeceuticals are the ingredients that have medicinal properties that benefits topical action and also Provide protection against degenerative skin condition. The present work was carried out by using these Ingredients that have less side effects. Products used to protect lips rather than to decorate them are well Known as lip balms. They form an adherent, moisture resistant film of oily substances. Usually without any Dye. Current study showed that the natural cosmetics are one of the most preferred skin care globally because they are believing to be safer than their chemically-based relatives and because they may cover the skin from harmful UV radiation. Lipstick, or crayon lip colour, is a cosmetic product that provides colour, texture, and protection to the lips via the use of pigments, oils, waxes, and emollients. Lipstick is one of the most popular makeup items. Some lip colours can be used as lip balms to keep your lips soft and glossy. It is a popular cosmetic option that may be made from either natural or artificial ingredients. Some of the heavy metals used in synthetic lipsticks are absorbed by the lips and stomach after application. These metals include nickel, copper, chromium, arsenic, and cobalt. The remaining is taken up by the skin's melanin and combines with other chemicals in the environment to produce a rash that most noticeably affects the lips. So, the lipsticks in particular need to be tested for irritation since they are applied directly to the lips, which may be quite sensitive. A precautionary skin and lip test is still necessary to rule out the risk of an allergic reaction. In contrast to the harmful consequences of synthetic chemicals, the herbal term serves as a symbol of protection for people's

well-being. Compresses, tonics, pastes, shampoos, sindoor, birth control, and even lipstick made from herbs are all on the rise in popularity. 4–6 Herbal cosmetics are becoming more popular since they are safe for the skin and don't cause any irritation or other problems. Herbal cosmetics are sometimes commonly referred to as "natural cosmetics." First, a natural base is made, into which one or more herbal constituents are carefully combined. 3–5 Lip colouring has been a tradition since the prehistoric era. In recent days the usage of producing Current era, lipsticks contain various hazardous chemicals that might cause health issues (dermatitis, allergy, dryness on lip). It turns the lips a dark shade of black as well. Synthetic dyes are very harmful if ingested by the user. In the worst case, it might lead to a dangerous type of cancer and other diseases. For this reason, in the current study, we can develop an herbal lipstick using various herbal pigments and mould. In addition, cosmetic companies hire specialized teams of scientists to develop and test each new line of Makeup, fragrances, lotions, soaps, and more. Lip balms are formulated to be applied to the lips to Prevent dryness and protect against various environmental factors. To create a lip balm formula, it is Necessary to balance the concentration of key ingredients including butters, oils and waxes for the final Product to work and apply. The beauty of lips can be enhanced by Lip colour; it also enhances the overall Charm of the face. Various makeup and lip care products mainly include lipstick, lip balm, lip balm. The Main role of lip care products is to create attractiveness, moisturize, protect lips from harmful UV rays, Etc. The skin on the lips is thin and different from other parts of the body. It has no hair follicles, Sebaceous glands and sweat. It lacks an inherent mechanism to retain moisture and protect from the External environment. Therefore, the lips of need more care, protection and moisture retention. Poor quality products can cause dryness and

pigmentation or discoloration of the lips. Especially some Ingredients like phenol or menthol are harmful to the lips.

Lip balm:

Lip balm is a wax-like substance applied topically to the lips to moisturize. Lip balms are designed to protect the lips from the external environment Like cold in winter and prevent drying, chapping of lips. The protection of lips helps to prevent Irritation and infection. Occlusive lip balms Prevent saliva from wetting the skin repeatedly. The minimum consumer expectation for lip balm is to form a thin film on the lips. Therefore, the preparation of the recipe is a less complicated task. It is recommended to apply lip balm on the lip line before applying matte lipstick because the balm helps to fix the lipstick in place. It's cheaper than lipstick. Lip balm is a moisturizer applied to the lips to keep the lips from drying out and to protect the lips from environmental factors. Although the same applies to lipstick because it is a cosmetic form that closely resembles lip balm, the cosmetic literature has very little data on this type of formulation (in stick form). Lip balm and lip gloss are not interchangeable, the former being a product that can be used by both men and women. Fatty acids, such as waxes, oils, and butters, are the main

ingredients of lipsticks, giving them their consistency and acting as emollients. Castor oil, beeswax, carnauba wax, candelilla wax, paraffin, and cocoa butter are some of the most common. However, there are a few key differences between lipstick and lip balm, especially in terms of function: lipstick serves to colour the lips, while lip balm protects them. In addition, lipstick formulations are more complex than lip balm formulations due to the increasing number of ingredients. To make a lip balm, the concentrations of key ingredients, such as butter, oils and waxes, must be Balanced so that the final product has a melting point of 59-60° C. Formula will have different quality depending on wax, oil, ratio and colour. A high proportion of waxes and pigments can be used to create a long-wearing product, while the opposite can result in a smoother lipstick or lip balm. The chemicals in lip balm formulations can adversely affect softness and breaking point, which are two distinct characteristics. There can exist two formulations with the same melting point but different consistency. It can take a lot of effort to overcome these problems. For a formula to have the proper melting, softening and breaking points, a balance must be achieved between the ingredients.

Anatomy of Lip:

Fig 1. Anatomy Of Lips

The 5 main areas are vermilion/white roll, sub vermilion, peristomal, philtral column and commissure. The subcutaneous part corresponds to the dry mucosal lip and the peristalsis corresponds to the junction of the dry and wet mucosal lips. The vermilion/white roll can be split on the upper lip to include the Lateral and apex areas of the cupid and the central filter areas, while the vermilion lower lip is divided into the middle and beside. The sub vermilion is divided into medial and lateral regions, and the Peristalsis into medial and lateral regions. Lips: The surface of the lips consists of four areas: hairy skin, Vermilion rim, vermilion mucosa, and cheeks. The normal shape of the lips changes with age and is strongly influenced by ethnicity.

1. **Vermilion:** The red part of the lips. It is covered by a specialized stratified squamous epithelium.
2. **Cisconium border:** The border of the lighter skin separates the vermilion from the surrounding skin.
3. **Cupid's bow:** the border formed by the vermilion edge of the upper lip.

4. **Mouth:** The opening is limited by the upper and lower cinnabar.
5. **Corner of the mouth:** The meeting place of the sides of the upper and Lower lips.

The upper and lower lips contain mucous membranes, vermilion, and skin surfaces. This Article provides a brief overview of the anatomy, neurovascular, and musculoskeletal systems of the lip, as well as important clinical and surgical considerations related to lip pathology. While lip Considerations typically focus on the vermilion area, the upper lip extends from the nasolabial fold to the Lower edge of the nose, and the lower lip includes the area between the lateral margins and the inner lip Crease of the chin.

Lip Disorders:

1. **Dry lips:** When the lips lose moisture and become dried, dry lips develop. Environmental Variables like low temperatures, dry air, or very frequent lip-licking can all contribute to this. Lips that are dry can feel tight, split, and even peel.

2. **Chapped Lips:** A more extreme form of dryness, chapped lips can be painful, Uncomfortable, and even bleed. Long-term dryness, sun exposure, wind exposure, or severe Weather can all lead to chapped lips.
3. **Fever Blisters:** Also known as cold sores, fever blisters are tiny, uncomfortable, fluid-filled Blisters that develop on or around the lips. The herpes simplex virus is the culprit behind Them, and are highly contagious. Cold sores can be recurrent and tend to flare up during Periods of stress or illness.
4. **Angular cheilitis:** An inflammation and cracking of the mouth's corners are symptoms of the Illness known as angular cheilitis. It may result from conditions including bacterial or yeast Infections, poor nutrition, or protracted moisture exposure.
5. **Lip infections:** Bacteria, viruses, or fungus can cause an infection on the lips. Swelling, Redness, discomfort, and the development of pus-filled blisters or sores are all signs of Infection.
6. **Allergic responses:** Some people may experience allergic responses to certain components in Food, cosmetics, or lip care products. Swelling, itching, redness, and even lip blistering are all Symptoms of allergic responses.
7. **Lip discoloration:** Numerous factors, such as sun exposure, smoking, some medicines, or Underlying medical disorders, can cause changes in lip color. Lips might seem darker in this condition.
8. **Sores:** A raised area or hard sore on the lip May be a form of skin cancer. Other sores can develop as symptoms of other medical conditions, such as an infection with the herpes simplex virus of the mouth or syphilis. Still others, such as keratoacanthoma, have no known cause. Lip balms are formulated to be applied to the lips to prevent dryness and protect them from environmental aggressors. Currently on the market there are many types of chemical lip balms from brands such as the body shop, Nivea, Himalaya, Blistex, etc. The cosmetic literature reports limited data on this type of formulation, although references to lipstick apply as it is a cosmetic form similar to lip balm. Lip balm should not be considered the equivalent of lip gloss, the former being a product for both men and women. Lips contain melanin, which helps protect the skin from the sun's harmful rays. But then the use of ingredients like ghee, honey, vitamin E, etc. keep lips hydrated for a long time.

Fig 2.1. Lip Infection

Fig 2.2. Angular Cheilitis

Fig 2.4. Sores.

Fig 2.5. Lip discoloration |

Fig 2.5. Fever Blisters

Fig 2.6. Dry Lips

Advantages of Lip Balm:

Lip balm helps protect the health and natural beauty of the lips.

1. Sunscreen lip balm has been shown to block UV damage to the lips.
2. They are not gender-specific products and can be used by both men and women.
3. Lip balm helps protect sore, chapped and dry lips.

4. The product in contact with the skin should not cause friction or dryness, and must form an even layer on the lips to protect the lip lining which is sensitive to environmental factors such as UV rays, drought and pollution.

5. It refreshes, refreshes and also treats lip related symptoms caused by colds, flu and allergies.

6. The use of natural lip cosmetics to treat skin appearance and condition.

FIG 3. Beetroot Lipbalm

Common Ingredients Used in Natural Lip Balm Formulation:

Base:

Waxes form an important group of ingredients for the manufacture of personal care products and decorative cosmetics. Waxes are used in different industries and products. They are predominately used in candles, but also find important applications in food, cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries as thickeners/emulsifiers. Chemically, waxes are complex mixtures of hydrocarbons and fatty acids combined with esters. Waxes are harder, less greasy and more brittle than fats. They are very resistant to moisture, oxidization and bacteria. There are four categories of waxes as: (a) Animal Waxes: Beeswax, lanolin, spermaceti; (b) Plant Waxes: Carnauba, candelilla, jojoba; (c) Mineral Waxes: Ozokerite, paraffin, microcrystalline, ceresin; (d) Synthetic Waxes: Polyethylene, carbowax, acrawax, stearon. The most widely used waxes for cosmetic products are beeswax, carnauba and candelilla wax. Waxes are esters of a fatty acid and a fatty alcohol. Jojoba oil is therefore a wax, not oil. Physically, waxes are characterized by a high melting point (50-100°C).

The most used wax is beeswax which is a good emollient and thickener. Two other natural waxes often used in cosmetics are carnauba and candelilla wax. Both are harder and have a higher melting point making them more stable and suitable for dry products e.g. lip balm. Cocoa butter is a natural fat that comes from cocoa bean and It gives a creamy softness to the lip balm. It will nourish and Moisturize lips and help heal chapped and dry lips because it Contains antioxidants. Another important and useful Component of lip balm is white beeswax with melting point 59°-60°C. It usefully binds oils and high melting point waxes. It is used in 3 to 10% of the total formula. It shrinks on Cooling and thus helps preparation of molded products. At Higher concentration it produces a dull way appearance and Causes the balm to crumble during use. Candelilla wax has a melting point 65°-69°C and can be is Used in 5-10% of formulation. A mixture of candelilla wax and beeswax is very good for making lip balm. If candelilla Wax is used to a little in an excess than beeswax the product Gets a smooth and glossy appearance. On the other side Carnauba wax increases the melting point of the base and Hardens the lip balm therefore used in

very small amounts. It Brings an attractive luster to the products.

Oils

Oils and fats are differing in their physical forms; generally, the latter are solid at room temperature. Both fats and oils are Chemically glycerol esters composed of glycerol and fatty Acids and are also called as triglycerides. Fatty acids can be saturated or unsaturated, thereby Determining the stability and property of the oil. Oils with a High degree of saturated fatty acids (lauric, myristic, palmitic and stearic acids) include coconut oil, cottonseed oil, and Palm oil. Oils with a high degree of unsaturated fatty acids (oleic, arachidonic, linoleic acid) are canola oil, olive oil, Corn oil, almond oil, safflower oil, castor oil and avocado oil. Saturated oils are more stable and do not become rancid as Quickly as unsaturated oils. However, unsaturated oils are Smoother, more precious, less greasy, and better absorbed by The skin. Natural butters like shea butter, avocado butter or Cocoa butter are not true butters but natural fats. In general, Natural butters are excellent emollients and thickeners and Dependent on the type may have various additional properties (e.g. antioxidant & and soothing properties in shea and Avocado butter due to phenolic compounds). The oil mixture is required to blend properly with the waxes to provide a suitable film on the applied lip skin. An ideal Mixture is one which enables the product to spread easily and Produces a thin film with good covering power. Sunflower or olive oil, both oils will give a great gloss to lips. Castor oil is used in many lip balms because of its good Qualities, though now days some other oils or solvents are Being used. A refined grade castor oil is of good color and is Odourless and tasteless. Castor oil is a very good plasticizing Agent. An antioxidant is to be added to the castor oil against Rancidification though it is not as prone to rancidification as Other

vegetable oils like olive oil or almond oil. Jojoba oil is known for its skin-softening properties which Can prevent lips from dehydrating. While wolfberry seed oil Is renowned for its moisturizing and skin conditioning Properties. Rosehip oil is excellent for maintaining then Natural moisture balance in skin. Vitamin E is a well-known Antioxidant that plays an essential role in the lip balm base. Peppermint essential oil energizes and revitalizes skin. Cinnamon essential oil is an excellent antioxidant. Lavender Essential oil is soothing and nourishing to skin. And Grapefruit essential oil is light and refreshing for dry lips. Almond oil is pale yellow oil with slight characteristic Odour. It consists of glycerides chiefly of oleic acid with Smaller amounts of other acids namely, linoleic, myristic and Palmitic. It has emollient properties.

Colouring Agent

Colorants or coloring agents are mainly used to impart a Distinctive appearance to the Cosmetic products. Color has been used in cosmetics since early times. Basically, a desire to buy a cosmetic product is controlled by three Senses namely sight, touch and smell. As such as, color is an Important ingredient of cosmetic formulations [18]. The color Is imparted to the lips in two ways; (a) By staining the skin with a solution of dyestuff which can penetrate the outer layer of the lip skin, (b) By covering the lips with a colored layer Which serves to hide any skin roughness and give a smooth Appearance. The first requirement is met by soluble dyes and The second one is met is insoluble dyes and pigments which Make the film more or less opaque. Modern lip balms contain Both to achieve the combined effect. The colors should be from the list of certified dyes under the drugs and cosmetics Act. The naturally occurring colors from different plant and fruit sources are listed. The colorant derived from natural source

should be nontoxic with no physiological activity. It should be a definite Chemical compound because then only its coloring power will Be reliable, its assay will be practicable and easier. Its Tinctorial (coloring) power should be high enough so that Only small quantities would be sufficient for use. Colorants Should be unaffected by light, tropical temperatures, Hydrolysis and micro-organisms and therefore they must be Stable on storage. Colorants should not have affected by oxidizing or reducing agents and pH changes and also should not interferes with the tests and assays. Water soluble colorants are equally desirable with Oil-soluble and spirit-soluble colors. The most important Characteristic of colorants is compatibility with other Ingredients and medicament. It should be free from Objectionable taste and odour and must be readily available and inexpensive. The examples of natural colorants Are obtained from beet root, saffron, turmeric, etc. Saffron is Dried stigma of flowers of the plant *Cross Sativuslinne*. It is a Perennial plant and is grown in Kashmir in India. It is also Cultivated in Spain, France, Greece and Iran. The principle Coloring agent in saffron is crocin. Crocin is yellow powder, a Glycoside in nature and easily soluble in water.

Flavouring Agent

Flavours or flavouring agent are usually required to mask the four basic taste sensations. Flavour refers to a mixed sensation of taste, touch, smell, sight and sound, all of which involve a combination of physiochemical and physiological actions that influence the perception of substances. With the expansion of technology in the flavour industry, many artificial or imitation flavours have been created. The creation of an acceptable flavour is more of an art than a science. Flavourants are selected on the basis of the taste of the drug

or other ingredients need to be incorporated. Flavours used in lip balm should not contain any ingredient which may be irritating or toxic. These should have good taste and should be able to mask fatty odour of the base. Flavouring agents are an essential component to mask the odour of the fatty or wax base as well as to impart an attractive flavor. They are normally used in the concentration range of 2-4% of total formulation. Flavour should be stable and compatible with the other constituents of the lip balm. The flavours should not be very strong as to clash with or overpower other flavors that may be used concurrently with the lip balm. Perfumes of the fruit flavor type have been advocated as well. Also something edible can be used. The commonly used flavours are apricot, strawberry, raspberry, cherry, honey, etc. Honey has the capacity to serve as a natural food preservative.

Formula for Lip balm:

Beeswax: Beeswax is used in lip balms, lip glosses, hand creams, ointments, and moisturizers. And in Cosmetics such as eyeshadow, blush and eyeliner. Beeswax is also an important ingredient in Mustache and hair waxes, making hair smooth and shiny. Typically, beeswax is used in makeup Products because it is a natural emulsifier, allowing liquid and oily makeup ingredients to bind and Hold. It increases the thickness of solid products like lipstick, giving them structure, and the keeps Them solid for smooth application.

Cocoa Butter: Cocoa butter is an emollient and an excellent source of natural antioxidants. It adds a Moisturizing protective layer to the lips, helping to protect them from extremes and indoor Temperatures that can dry out your lips. Cocoa butter melts at skin temperature, making it the Ingredient of choice in many skin care products, including scrubs, lotions, and soaps. Cocoa butter Lipstick is the perfect lip balm.

Coconut Oil: The moisturizing and emollient properties of coconut oil make it potentially helpful in Soothing dry, chapped lips. It is commonly used in lip balms, other lip products, and many other Beauty and self-care products. It absorbs quickly and leaves skin soft and radiant. In particular, as a Lip balm, it replenishes moisture and helps hydrate dry skin. If your lips are chapped, adding coconut Oil to your lip care routine will help moisturize and maintain their softness.

Method of Lip Balm Preparation:

The Preparation of Lip Balm includes the following steps:

Bring the Beetroot and Wash it properly. Remove the upper layer of the Beetroot and then cut it into pieces. Grind it into the mixer. The Beetroot juice is prepared. Take juice quantity as Other measures of ingredients are taken with respect to the proper fulfillment of the quantity required. Take 30 ml beetroot juice in measuring cylinder. Weigh 3.6 gm beeswax and cocoa butter. Take the 20 ml coconut oil in measuring cylinder. Then heat the

beetroot juice slowly on the burner by taking it into beaker. Stir the juice by pouring slowly the coconut oil into the beaker. Stir upto the formation of caramelization of the juice phase. Then keep aside the beaker to come at normal temperature. Take the bees wax and cocoa butter and melt it. After melting both add them into the caramelized formation of juice. Add 2 capsules of vitamin E. Add colouring agent, flavouring agent and fragrance in it. Then Stir gradually to mix both the phases better keep it on Ice bath and mix slowly. Keep few minutes in refrigerator. Then the lipbalm is prepared.

Formula for lip balm: -

Sr. No	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3
1	Cocca Butter	2.7g	3.6 g	3.6 g
2	Bees wax	2.7 g	3.6 g	3.6 g
3	Beet root juice	25 ml	35 ml	30 ml
4	Coconut Oil	20 ml	15 ml	20 ml
5	Vit E Capsules	2 Capsules	2 Capsules	2 Capsules

Fig 4. Carmelization

Evaluation Parameters:

Organoleptic Properties

The formulation was studied for physical Appearance, colour and odour. These Characteristics Were Evaluated by physical Observation. Texture and homogeneity were tested by pressing a small quantity of The Formulation between the thumb and index finger. The presence of coarse particles and Consistency Were used to evaluate the texture and homogeneity of the formulations. Skin feel (including stiffness, Greasiness, and grittiness) was also evaluated.

Texture: After formulating the lipbalm, we made sure that they were the right shade, had the proper amount of shine, and had a smooth and creamy texture.

Greasiness:

The oil test was reviewed to determine the amount of oil in a formulated lip balm. In this study, 4 grams of lip balm was placed on filter paper and the sample was left at room temperature for 24 hours.

pH:

One gram of the preparation is dispersed in 25 ml of distilled water. The pH of the preparation was Determined using a pH meter (Mettler Toledo) pre-calibrated with standard buffer solutions (pH 5.5 and 6).

Melting Point

The melting point was determined using a Melting Point instrument (Veego, India). Briefly, one end of The capillary tube was sealed; formula is fed

from one end into the capillary to a certain height. The Capillary is introduced into the melting point apparatus and the temperature at which the molten mass is Recorded.

Spreadability Test

Spreadability is determined using a slide. The formulation is sandwiched between two blades and a load Is applied; the recipe has been spread on the slides. Visual observations were made regarding the Uniformity of the layer formation. For this test, the following criteria have been established:

G – Good: homogenous

I – Moderate homogeneity; leaves few stops

B – Bad: uneven

Sensitive Skin

This is done by applying the product as a patch to the skin for 30 minutes and observing for a reaction of:

N – No reaction

R – Skin redness

I – Irritation or itching

Stability Test

The formulation of the lip balm has been evaluated for stability for 30 days under various temperature Conditions mainly room temperature ($25\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), higher temperatures in the oven ($40\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and Refrigerator ($5\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). Characteristics such as organoleptic properties and Spreadability were evaluated On days 7, 15, and 30.

a. Preliminary Stability Test

Formula evaluated on preliminary stability tests including physical properties (color, odor and Appearance) and flow testing. Since this formula does not cause any physical or balance changes, it has Been tested for normal stability.

Beetroot Juice	Rich in vitamins and minerals that nourish the delicate skin of lips
Vitamin E Capsules	Prevents premature aging
Coconut oil	Gives natural shine and fuller look , intense hydration

b. Normal Stability Study

An amount of 25 g of the substance has been prepared for routine stability testing, where the physical Properties (color, odor, and appearance), flowability and the melting point was evaluated for 5 days at Room temperature. Samples are well preserved.

Fragrance Stability:

After 20 days, the fragrance/ stability of the herbal lipbalm composition was evaluated by inhaling a direct sample.

FIG 5. Melting Point

RESULT

Sr. No	Evaluation Parameter	Observation
1	Melting Point	59 - 60° C
2	Organoleptic Properties	
2.1	Colour	Light Pink
2.2	Odour	Pleasant
2.3	Appearance	Smooth
3	Spread ability	Good
4	pH measure	6
5	Skin Irritation	No

FIG 6. PH Determination

Ingredients	Properties
Cocca Butter	An exceptional emollient, deeply hydrating the lips
Bees Wax	Creates a breathable barrier on the lips, helping to shield from the environmental factors like wind, cold, and sun

FIG 7. Spreadability

Here's How to Apply Lip Balm for the Best Protection:

Step 1: Open the lid of the container. If the balm is in a tube, you only need to lift it about half an inch. If it's in the container, apply a pea-sized amount to your finger.

Step 2: Apply to lower lip. Rub the balm onto your lower lip, along the outside.

Step 3: Apply to upper lip. Rub the balm onto your upper lip, along the outside.

Step 4: Rub your lips together. Rub your upper and lower lips together. This helps distribute the balm evenly throughout your mouth.

How Often Should You Apply Lip Balm?

According to dermatologists, you should only apply lip balm a few times a day. Most experts recommend applying it in the following situations:

1. When you wake up in the morning
2. After eating or drinking
3. When you go to bed at night.

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CONCLUSION:

The present study aimed to create a lip balm with as many natural elements as feasible. The main colouring and flavouring ingredients were beetroot extract, beeswax, cocoa wax, vitamin E capsules, and coconut oil. Coconut oil served as the moisturising agent. Researchers looked examined how these components affected the formulation's physical features, including spread ability, uniformity, and organoleptic characteristics. It may be said that using these natural components helped create a great lip balm composition. Findings of numerous studies suggested that the recipe was safe to use and cleared various physical tests. According to stability information, the mixture should be stored at room temperature. In the future, natural bases like cocoa butter, beeswax, etc. could take the place of the paraffin wax that was employed as a base for the existing formulation.

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